

SOUND-ACCOMPANYING MOVEMENTS ENHANCE PERCEIVED AROUSAL IN MUSIC PERFORMANCE EVEN FROM A DISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an experiment measuring the impact of visual cues on the perception of music performance under varying static and dynamic visual conditions. Perceived arousal was measured in an audio-visual experiment using English horn performances. Audio and video recordings were made in a concert hall from short and long distance with and without sound-accompanying movements. Participants (N=32) rated perceived arousal continuously during watching, listening, or watching and listening. Sound-accompanying movements enhanced perceived arousal in audio-visual compared to auditory-only perception, while an immobile performance had a diminishing effect. In all sensory modalities, less arousal was perceived at longer distance. However, the positive effect of sound-accompanying movements in the visual channel was stronger than the negative effect of distance which is caused by both auditory and visual cues. Thus, through the visual channel, sound-accompanying movements may compensate for being seated far away from the performer at a concert.

1. INTRODUCTION

For each member of a concert audience, the experience is a unique combination of multisensory perception of music performance, transmission of the auditory, visual, and vibrotactile cues in the concert hall, and a specific social frame [1]. This study investigates the importance of visual information to the concert experience in an ecological setting but limited scope, focusing on audio-visual interactions in perceived arousal under varying visual conditions.

The high importance of visual cues to the perception of music performance is by now well known. In continuous measurements of musical tension, both auditory and visual channels were found to be important and reliable, although not necessarily correlated, sources of information [2]. The auditory channel is often thought to dominate; yet, mounting behavioral and physiological evidence shows that audio-visual perception of lower-level at-

tributes such as tension and arousal is driven by both channels [3, 4].

Visual information also impacts many higher-level aspects of music performance. Visual kinematic cues may in fact communicate expressiveness and expressive intentions more effectively than auditory cues [5, 6], possibly through coding loudness variation [7]. Visual information seems to weigh more in judgments of performance quality and expertise [8–11] and player identification [12]. Through body gestures, performers also communicate specific emotions [13] as well as their musical role in the ensemble [14].

In a live concert, both auditory and visual cues travel to the receiver over a distance. Research into the influence of visual conditions is limited in scope, however. Impact of visual cues has been shown on judgments of loudness and reverberance in auditoriums [15] and on room acoustic experience in virtual reality [16]. Static cues such as viewing angle, distance to stage, and size of photographic stage view were significant predictors of opera seat preference, although second to sound intensity [17]. Results from game research suggest that players experience greater arousal and immersion with a larger screen [18].

An experiment was carried out to explore the importance of visual cues under varying visual conditions in a concert hall performance. Earlier measurements show that participants perceive arousal in a coordinated way from both auditory and visual cues [4]. Two more independent variables were now added: observer's distance from the stage and the amount of sound-accompanying movements [19] exerted by the performer. This allowed separating the effects of static visual cues (viewing conditions) and dynamic visual cues (sound-accompanying movements). Response variable was perceived arousal, measured continuously over time [20, 21]. For better control over the experimental conditions, recorded performances were used.

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Stimuli, Design, and Participants

All stimuli consisted of a three-minute excerpt from the beginning of *In Nomine* for English horn by György Kurtág (1926-). The soloist, an early-career professional, was placed at center stage, ca 1 m from the front edge, in a 400-seat concert hall. Recordings were made with and without sound-accompanying movements from two positions in the concert hall as presented in Figure 1. Audio-

Figure 1. Performer (●) and recording (★) positions in the concert hall.

video recordings were made using one video camera and a stereo microphone pair placed at camera position. The relative differences in sound intensity and size of the stage view caused by the near and far recording positions were preserved.

Three predictors (independent variables) were manipulated in the experimental design as follows:

- Distance with two levels: [Near, Far]. The Near recordings were made from the first row, at a distance of ca 2.7 m to the performer. The Far recordings were made from row 11 at a distance of ca 13 m.
- Movement with two levels: [Move, Stay]. In the Move condition, the performer exerted sound-accompanying movements in addition to necessary sound-producing gestures. She was instructed to use her own movement repertoire in a way that would be congruent with the tempo and loudness variation of the music. The Stay condition consisted of sound-producing gestures without intentional sound-accompanying movements.
- Modality with three levels: [Auditory only (A), visual only (V), audio-visual (AV)]. The A condition consisted in audio recordings without video, the V condition in silent video recordings, and the AV condition in synchronized and congruent audio and video recordings.

N=32 subjects took part in the experiment (15 F / 17 M, aged M=24, sd=2.6; all but one were music students). Dis-

(a) Near, Move

(b) Far, Stay

Figure 2. Still images from the videos in two of the four conditions. Images are cropped and downsized but relative image sizes are preserved.

tance was a nested factor so that half of the participants rated Near recordings and the other half rated Far recordings. Within the Distance groups, Movement and Modality were crossed such that each participant rated all six resulting combinations: A-Move, A-Stay, AV-Move, AV-Stay, V-Move, and V-Stay. This grouping was a compromise between recruitment efforts, effective data collection, and reduced repetition of the material. The Near and Far groups were separated in order to prevent the possibility of forming expectations based on the other distance condition.

2.2 Measurement

Participants rated perceived arousal during watching and/or listening. Perceived arousal was defined as a measure of how much energy, activity, or tension the performance contains at any given moment. Audio was presented through headphones and video on a 24-inch monitor in full-screen mode. Participants sat at a normal working dis-

tance from the screen. The six three-minute stimuli were presented in randomized order, and participants gave responses by adjusting a slider continuously throughout the excerpts. The range of the slider end points was [0,1], and the values were read into a time series at a frequency of 4 Hz.

2.3 Data Pre-Processing

The raw measurement data were registered in order to compensate for slight differences in tempi and length of section breaks in the stimuli. The performer played systematically slightly faster and took shorter breaks between sections when adding sound-accompanying movements. Within sections the tempi were stable, however. The recordings were annotated manually according to ten sections and two major section breaks, and the time scales of all measurements were linearly adjusted so that section durations matched to the slowest stimulus which was the Near-Stay version. The length of each registered time series was again cut to 180 seconds.

2.4 Statistical Model

The data were analysed by means of functional analysis of variance (fANOVA), a technique suited to describe variability in a functional (time-varying) response curve in terms of predictors that can be either curves or scalars [22]. A functional additive regression model was constructed that contains both functional and scalar components for each predictor, decomposing the effects of the predictors into curves and constant shifts as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(t) \sim & f.\text{general}(t) + \\
 & f.\text{modality}(t) + f.\text{movement}(t) + f.\text{distance}(t) + \\
 & \text{modality} + \text{movement} + \text{distance} + \\
 & \text{modality:movement} + \text{modality:distance} + \\
 & \text{movement:distance}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

where

- $y(t)$ is functional perceived arousal
- $f.\text{general}(t)$ is a common functional component
- $f.\text{modality}(t)$, $f.\text{movement}(t)$, and $f.\text{distance}(t)$ are effects of functional predictors
- modality , movement , and distance are effects of scalar predictors
- $:$ marks interactions between scalar predictors

The model was fit by approximate Bayesian inference in R [23] using integrated nested Laplace approximation available in the INLA package [24]. INLA is a fast and computationally effective alternative to Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling and can be used to solve temporal additive regression models [25].

3. RESULTS

Figures 3 and 4 present the estimated effects of the predictors in Eq. 1. The top panel of Figure 3 shows the general time-varying component, the mid panel the effects of modality, and the bottom panel the combined general trend and modality effects. It is seen that audio-visual presentation has a general slight positive effect compared to both unimodal auditory or visual conditions.

Figure 4 shows the remaining effects of movement and distance after the general trend and modality effects have been extracted. Differences are mainly caused by distance in the auditory only condition and by movement in the visual only condition. In audio-visual perception, both effects are equally present. The combined effect is the most negative for the Stay-Far combination, while the Stay-Near and Move-Far combinations result in similar net effects, second only to the Move-Near combination.

The complete model fit combines the effects shown in Figures 3 and 4. To investigate the significance of differences caused by various effect combinations, the remaining analysis will focus on the fitted posterior mean arousal functions and their 95% confidence bands, expressed as the range between the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of the estimated means. Differences between conditions are significant at instances where the respective confidence bands do not overlap.

Figure 5 presents the 95% confidence bands for the fitted means (grey bands) and the measured mean ratings (thin lines). The measured means are within the fitted confidence bands with small and momentary deviations. An exception is the first minute of the Near-Move-V condition, where the additive functional components do not entirely capture the perceived changes.

The findings seen in Figure 4 are shown in full context in Figures 5 and 6. They present the same data faceted differently: the former highlights the effect of movement and the latter the effect of distance. In the auditory-only condition, the confidence bands for Move and Stay conditions overlap entirely for both distance conditions in Figure 5, indicating that sound-accompanying movements do not influence auditory ratings. Auditory perceived arousal is slightly diminished by long distance as seen in Figure 6.

In the visual-only condition, distance has a similar, rather weak negative effect (Figure 6). In contrast, the difference between Move and Stay conditions in Figure 5 is large and the respective confidence bands do not overlap at all. Thus, the visual channel effectively conveys arousal information from sound-accompanying movements.

Influence of the visual channel is evident in the audio-visual condition, where the confidence bands for Move and Stay conditions in Figure 5 only overlap in the time period 120-160 s and 150-160 s for the Near and Far conditions, respectively. For the most part, sound-accompanying movements significantly enhance audio-visual perceived arousal through the visual channel, independently of observer's distance to the performer.

Finally, Figure 7 presents the interesting comparison between auditory-only and audio-visual perception. In presence of sound-accompanying movements, more arousal is

Figure 3. General trend and effects of modality from the statistical model (Eq. 1).

Figure 4. Effects of movement and distance from the statistical model in auditory only, visual only, and audio-visual conditions (Eq. 1).

perceived in the audio-visual condition, while in their absence, the opposite is true. Distance influences these results, however. In the Near-Move condition where visual cues are the most salient, audio-visual perception is significantly increased from the auditory-only condition almost throughout the stimulus. In the Far-Move condition, however, the difference is significant only momentarily. Similarly, in the Far-Stay condition where visual cues are the least salient, audio-visual perception is significantly diminished from the auditory-only condition and less so in the Near-Stay condition.

The above analysis focused on significant level differences between conditions. Another important aspect is the amount of perceived changes, described by variability over time. It is an indicator of how much information the stimulus conveys over each sensory modality.

For a rough comparison of variability, the boxplots in Figure 8 present the interquartile ranges of the fitted functional means for each stimulus. (This analysis excludes the first 10 seconds during which the rating profiles rise from zero.) In the auditory-only condition, variability is unaffected by added movements and slightly diminished by long distance. In the visual-only condition, the effect of distance is similar. However, variability is notably higher in presence of sound-accompanying movements, exceeding even the auditory-only condition. The joint effect in the audio-visual condition is a slightly higher variability with movements compared to auditory-only perception; lack of movements in turn does not notably affect variability.

The audio-visual enhancement can thus be observed in both mean arousal levels and perceived changes over time¹.

Figure 5. Effect of movement on perceived arousal. Grey bands: 95% functional confidence bands for fitted means; thin lines: measured means.

¹ Dataset and analysis are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6461144>

Figure 6. Effect of distance on perceived arousal. Grey-filled bands: 95% functional confidence bands for fitted means.

4. DISCUSSION

In this experiment, dynamic visual cues were varied through the amount of sound-accompanying movements. These movements did not affect perceived arousal in the auditory-only condition. Through visual cues, however, they significantly enhanced perceived arousal in audio-visual perception; respectively, their absence had a diminishing effect. The significance of visual cues is in line with earlier results on audio-visual interactions in perception of changes in expressive intentions [6].

Static visual cues were varied through distance to the performer. The main effect of distance was similar in all sensory modalities (A / AV / V): slightly higher average arousal and more changes were perceived near the performer, both in absence and presence of movements. This was expected, as both auditory and visual cues are most salient at short distance. For auditory cues, this may be explained through concert hall acoustics. In the reverberant field, sound intensity decays in a concert hall somewhat, but not as much as it would with distance in free field. The amount of motion in the video recordings is in turn directly connected to distance through image size, and kinematic cues as well as facial expressions are more visible from close distance. Importantly however, perceived arousal in the visual-only condition did not decrease dramatically with distance; the results might be different if physiological responses were measured.

The joint effect of static and dynamic visual cues was the most negative at long distance without movements, where perceived arousal was significantly diminished in audio-visual compared to auditory-only perception (Figure 7, lower right panel). This loss was compensated for by added movements (Figure 7, upper right panel). It is of course a limitation that both distance and movement were varied on only two levels; in a live concert, these both vary

Figure 7. Comparison between audio-only and audio-visual conditions: 95% functional confidence bands for fitted means.

at a wide range with seating and performance style. However, rather than short distance to the stage, presence of salient dynamic visual cues seems to be key. Immobile performance, instead of being ignored, leads to reduced audio-visual perception. In such cases, concert-goers may easily optimize their perceived arousal by closing their eyes – at the cost of losing visual information entirely, of course.

In audio-visual perception, congruent sound-accompanying movements enhanced perceived variation in arousal even though no effect was present in auditory-only perception. As perceived changes in arousal correlate with loudness/intensity changes over time [26], a similar enhancement could be achieved by presenting auditory-only stimuli with enhanced dynamic range. On the other hand, studies on perceived quality of concert hall acoustics show that preferred halls reproduce loudness variation especially well [27]. An interesting continuation for this research might be to explore cross-modal enhancement of perceived concert hall acoustics by adding salient and congruent visual stimuli.

4.1 Limitations

Participants in this study were musically trained with one exception. Adding a group of non-musicians as participants would produce important knowledge about differences between these groups. In auditory perception, previous research reports very similar emotional responses of both musicians and non-musicians to measures including musical tension and magnitude of esthetic experience [28–30]. However, musical training has been shown to alter both the behavioural and neural processing of sadness and fear [31] and the emotional impact of tempo differences [32]. In visual or audio-visual perception, no effects of musical training were observed on perceived ten-

Figure 8. Boxplots of fitted values for all factor combinations. Interquartile ranges of the fitted functional means allow a rough comparison of perceived changes for each stimulus.

sion [33]. In a study on perceived effort and arousal, musicians gave slightly higher ratings in the auditory only condition and non-musicians in the visual only condition, although the analysis was not conclusive [4]. Claims have been made, however, that musically unskilled listeners perceive the performer’s emotional intentions entirely through visual cues [34]. This evidence leads to a future hypothesis that non-musicians might rate the auditory channel rather similarly but perhaps rely more on visual information, which would rather emphasize the effect reported in the current study.

For the sake of systematic control of the conditions, the current results were obtained from recordings observed in a laboratory setting. Extrapolating them to witnessing a live performance is of course difficult. A live performance is thought to enhance the experience in many ways [35], and previous research has shown higher emotional convergence between audience members in a live concert [36]. Less is known about the perception of basic emotional dimensions such as arousal in live versus recorded performances. The basic trends should hold in both cases: perceived arousal decreases with decreasing loudness and slightly with decreasing image size, and congruent movements may enhance it through the visual channel. At each seat position in the concert hall, these factors have an individual impact. The resulting net effect should therefore also vary almost continuously.

Objective acoustic and visual analysis of the stimuli was not part of this investigation. In an earlier dataset, collected from sound-producing movements in cello performance [4], ratings correlated highly with simple predictors: auditory ratings with RMS energy, roughness, and event density, and visual ratings with the amount of motion (expressed as root-mean-square of differenced head and finger positions). A deeper analysis should include these time-varying predictors as well as measures of fa-

cial expressions and muscle tension. This work, along with comparison of models including interactions between functional predictors, is left for a future investigation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It was shown how sound-accompanying movements can enhance, and how their absence can diminish audio-visual perceived arousal in music. In both sensory modalities, higher average arousal and more changes were perceived near the performer than further away. In audio-visual perception the effect of distance, caused by changes in both auditory and visual cues, may be compensated for by the positive effect of sound-accompanying movements. These results add to the mounting body of evidence that visual information influences our perception of music performance in numerous ways.

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6. REFERENCES

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